

Correlation of HbA1C with Fundoscopic Finding in Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients

Anil Kumar¹, Neha², Madhuri Meena³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar, India

²Lady Medical Officer, P.S.M. Department Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar, India

³Professor, Department of Medicine, Jhalawar Medical College, Jhalawar, India

Received: 28-12-2021 / Revised: 15-01-2022 / Accepted: 08-02-2022

Corresponding author: Dr. Anil Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Diabetes is a very common disease now days. It has adverse effect on many human organs as its duration increases. Many studies exist to show its bad effects on body organs in different parts of world. We have studied is there any relation between fundoscopic finding with HbA1c levels.

Methods: we have done a cross sectional study from January 2016 to March 2017 in a tertiary health care hospital located in Jhalawar, Rajasthan. Our study includes all the known case of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients of age group of 45 years and above.

Results: It was seen that, 81 patients had grade 1 fundoscopic changes from which 14 (17.2%) shows Hb1Ac was less than 6.5% whereas 67(82.7%) had Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. 15 patients had grade 2 fundoscopic changes from which 1 (6%) had Hb1Ac level less than 6.5% and 14 (94%) had Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. 4 patients had grade 3 fundoscopic changes and all of them were having Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. This Fundoscopic finding was not statistically associated when compared with Hb1Ac. (Pearson Chi-Square- 1.854 with df 2 and p value is 0.396).

Conclusion: Fundoscopic changes in patients was not found associated with glycosylated haemoglobin as $p < 0.3$.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Fundoscopic, Glycosylated Hemoglobin, Retinopathy.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a group of metabolic disorders that share the phenotype of hyperglycemia. Several distinct types of diabetes mellitus are caused by a complex interaction of genetic and environmental factors. Depending on the etiology of diabetes mellitus, factors' contributing to hyperglycemia includes reduced insulin secretion, decreased

glucose utilization, and increased glucose production. The metabolic disregulation associated with DM causes secondary pathophysiologic changes in multiple organ system.

Diabetic Retinopathy:

Diabetic retinopathy may be the most common microvascular complication of diabetes. It is responsible for more than

10,000 new cases of blindness every year in the United States alone[1].

The risk of developing diabetic retinopathy or other microvascular complications of diabetes depends on both the duration and the severity of hyperglycemia. Development of diabetic retinopathy in patients with type 2 diabetes was found to be related to both severity of hyperglycemia and presence of hypertension in the U.K. Prospective Diabetes Study (UKPDS), and most patients with type 1 diabetes develop evidence of retinopathy within 20 years of diagnosis[2,3]. Retinopathy may begin to develop as early as 7 years before the diagnosis of diabetes in patients with type 2 diabetes. There are several proposed pathological mechanisms by which diabetes may lead to development of retinopathy.

Aldose reductase may participate in the development of diabetes complications. Aldose reductase is the initial enzyme in the intracellular polyol pathway. This pathway involves the conversion of glucose into glucose alcohol (sorbitol). High glucose levels increase the flux of sugar molecules through the polyol pathway, which causes sorbitol accumulation in cells. Osmotic stress from sorbitol accumulation has been postulated as an underlying mechanism in the development of diabetic microvascular complications, including diabetic retinopathy. In animal models, sugar alcohol accumulation has been linked to microaneurysm formation, thickening of basement membranes, and loss of pericytes. Treatment studies with aldose reductase inhibitors, however, have been disappointing[4]. Cells are also thought to be injured by glycoproteins. High glucose concentrations can promote the nonenzymatic formation of advanced glycosylated end products (AGEs). In animal models, these substances have also been associated with formation of

microaneurysms and pericytes loss. Evaluations of AGE inhibitors are underway.

Oxidative stress may also play an important role in cellular injury from hyperglycemia. High glucose levels can stimulate free radical production and reactive oxygen species formation. Animal studies have suggested that treatment with antioxidants, such as vitamin E, may attenuate some vascular dysfunction associated with diabetes, but treatment with antioxidants has not yet been shown to alter the development or progression of retinopathy or other microvascular complications of diabetes[5].

Growth factors, including vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), growth hormone, and transforming growth factor β , have also been postulated to play important roles in the development of diabetic retinopathy. VEGF production is increased in diabetic retinopathy, possibly in response to hypoxia. In animal models, suppressing VEGF production is associated with less progression of retinopathy[6]. Diabetic retinopathy is generally classified as either background or proliferative. It is important to have a general understanding of the features of each to interpret eye examination reports and advise patients of disease progression and prognosis.

Background retinopathy includes such features as small hemorrhages in the middle layers of the retina. They clinically appear as "dots" and therefore are frequently referred to as "dot hemorrhages." Hard exudates are caused by lipid deposition that typically occurs at the margins of hemorrhages. Microaneurysms are small vascular dilatations that occur in the retina, often as the first sign of retinopathy. They clinically appear as red dots during retinal examination. Retinal edema may result from microvascular leakage and is indicative of compromise of the blood-

retinal barrier. The appearance is one of greyish retinal areas. Retinal edema may require intervention because it is sometimes associated with visual deterioration[7]. Proliferative retinopathy is characterized by the formation of new blood vessels on the surface of the retina and can lead to vitreous hemorrhage. White areas on the retina (“cotton wool spots”) can be a sign of impending proliferative retinopathy. If proliferation continues, blindness can occur through vitreous hemorrhage and traction retinal detachment. With no intervention, visual loss may occur. Laser photocoagulation can often prevent proliferative retinopathy from progressing to blindness.

Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c): is a form of hemoglobin that is measured primarily to identify the three month average plasma glucose concentration, because the lifespan of a red blood cell is three months. It is formed in a nonenzymatic glycation pathway by hemoglobin's exposure to plasma glucose. HbA1c is a measure of the beta-N-1-deoxy fructosyl component of hemoglobin[5,6]. Normal levels of glucose produce a normal amount of glycated hemoglobin. As the average amount of

plasma glucose increases, the fraction of glycated hemoglobin increases in a predictable way. This serves as a marker for average blood glucose levels over the previous three months before the measurement as this is the lifespan of red blood cells. In diabetes mellitus, higher amounts of glycated hemoglobin, indicating poorer control of blood glucose levels, have been associated with cardiovascular disease, nephropathy, neuropathy, and retinopathy.

Measuring HbA1c: A number of techniques are used to measure hemoglobin A1c. Laboratories use: High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC): The HbA1c result is calculated as a ratio to total hemoglobin by using a chromatogram. Immunoassay, Enzymatic, Capillary electrophoresis, Boronate affinity chromatography. The United States, HbA1c testing laboratories are certified by the National Glycohemoglobin Standardization Program (NGSP) to standardize them against the results of the 1993 Diabetes Control and Complications In Trial (DCCT)[8] An additional percentage scale, Mono S is in use by Sweden and KO500 is in Japan[9,10].

Table 1: Rapid increase in the incidence of type 1 diabetes in Polish children from 1989 to 2004, and predictions for 2010 to 2025[11]

HbA1C (%)	(mmol/mol)	Estimated average glucose (mmol/L)	(mg/dL)
5	31	5.4 (4.2–6.7)	97 (76–120)
5	42	7.0 (5.5–8.5)	126 (100–152)
6	53	8.6 (6.8–10.3)	154 (123–185)
7	64	10.2 (8.1–12.1)	183 (147–217)
8	75	11.8 (9.4–13.9)	212 (170–249)
10	86	13.4 (10.7–15.7)	240 (193–282)
11	97	14.9 (12.0–17.5)	269 (217–314)
12	108	16.5 (13.3–19.3)	298 (240–347)
13	119	18.1 (15–21)	326 (260–380)
14	130	19.7 (16–23)	355 (290–410)
15	140	21.3 (17–25)	384 (310–440)
16	151	22.9 (19–26)	413 (330–480)
17	162	24.5 (20–28)	441 (460–510)
18	173	26.1 (21–30)	470 (380–540)
19	184	27.7 (23–32)	499 (410–570)

Observations of Measuring HbA1c

Inclusion Criteria

1. All patients of type 2 diabetes mellitus 45 years and above
2. Patients with or without micro vascular complication.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with secondary hyperglycemic states like hypothyroidism,
2. Proteinuric conditions like congestive cardiac failure, renal failure and proven renal diseases
3. Pregnancy.

Material and Method:

We have planned to select approximately 100 diabetic patients from OPD as well as IPD of medicine department. All the patients will go through the investigations for microalbuminuria and HbA1C. The samples were centrifuged, separated and stored at 4°C until analysis. For glycosylated hemoglobin estimation, EDTA blood samples were used. Glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) by the

cation exchange resin method and micro albumin levels in the urine sample by using the turbilatex method. The present cross sectional study is conducted from January 2016 to March 2017 in a tertiary health care hospital located in Jhalawar, Rajasthan. Our study includes all the known case of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients of age group of 45 years and above (according to American diabetes association). All the patients were fully informed about the purpose, the procedures and the hazards of the study.

Result:

Fundoscopic changes and Hb1Ac

14 and 67 patients had grade 1 fundoscopic changes and showing Hb1Ac level less than 6.5% and more than 6.5% respectively. 1 patient had grade 2 fundoscopic changes and showing Hb1Ac level less than 6.5% whereas 14 patients having grade 2 changes had Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. 4 patients had grade 3 fundoscopic changes and showing Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%.

Table 2: Comparison of HbA1c with Fundoscopic change

Hb1Ac	Fundus			Total
	1	2	3	
Less than 6.5%	14 (17.2%)	1 (6%)	0	15
more than 6.5%	67 (82.7%)	14 (94%)	4 (100%)	85
Total	81	15	4	100

Pearson Chi-Square- 1.854 with df 2 and p value is 0.396

Graph 1: Comparison of HbA1c with Fundoscopic changes

Fundoscopy changes

It was seen that, 81 patients had grade 1 fundoscopic changes from which 14 (17.2%) shows Hb1Ac was less than 6.5% whereas 67(82.7%) had Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. 15 patients had grade 2 fundoscopic changes from which 1 (6%) had Hb1Ac level less than 6.5% and 14 (94%) had Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. 4 patients had grade 3 fundoscopic changes and all of them were having Hb1Ac level more than 6.5%. This Fundoscopic finding was not statistically associated when compared with Hb1Ac. (Pearson Chi-Square- 1.854 with df 2 and p value is 0.396). (Table no -2, graph no-1)

One study conducted in Turkey, shows The frequency of diabetic (both NPDR and PDR) retinopathy was lowest in the group of diabetes with the lowest HbA1c concentration <6% (4.8% or 5/104), 8.7% or 12/137 in the group with HbA1c values between 6.1% and 6.9%, 62.8% or 121/195 in the group with HbA1c values between 7% and 9.9% and highest (82.2% or 150/182) in the group with HbA1c concentrations over 10%. As seen by the logistic regression analysis, in patients who had HbA1c value of 7%-9.9% there

were significant relationship between DR and HbA1c levels (p=0.001)[12].

Study conducted by Priyadharshini N., shows that HbA1c was found to be significantly associated with maculopathy (clinically significant macular oedema with p = 0.003). Distribution based on duration was found to be 45% in those with disease greater than 15 years, 40 % with disease greater than 10 years and 15% with disease less than 10 years. When the subgroups with maculopathy were analysed, a statistical significant difference was noted with p=0.03 in those with high Hba1c levels but no difference was noted in terms of duration of the diabetes mellitus and the age groups affected[13]

Conclusion:

Fundoscopy changes in patients was not found associated with glycosylated haemoglobin as p <0.3.

Limitations:

One of the biggest challenges for health care providers today is addressing the continued needs and demands of individuals with chronic illnesses like diabetes. During study, only 100 patients were agreed and included in the study.

More sample size will require generalizing its effect on population. Many patients didn't agree to participate in study because of many problems like no time to participate in the study, have ignorance towards the diseases etc. We did not exclude obese patients. Ours is cross sectional study so we cannot compare efficacy of HbA1c levels in controlling and prevention of microvascular complication in diabetic patients.

References:

1. Fong DS, Aiello LP, Ferris FL 3rd, Klein R: Diabetic retinopathy. *Diabetes Care* 27:2540 - 2553, 2004
2. UK Prospective Diabetes Study Group. Intensive blood glucose control with sulphonylureas or insulin compared with conventional treatment and risk of complications in patients with type 2 diabetes (UKPDS 33). *Lancet*. 1998; 352:837-853
3. Keenan HA, Costacou T, Sun JK, Doria A, Cavallerano J, Coney J, Orchard TJ, Aiello LP, King GL: Clinical factors associated with resistance to microvascular complications in diabetic patients of extreme disease duration: the 50-year medalist study. *Diabetes Care* 30: 2007; 1995-1997.
4. Gabbay KH: Hyperglycemia, polyol metabolism, and complications of diabetes mellitus. *Annu Rev Med* 1975; 26:521 -536.
5. Kunisaki M, Bursell SE, Clermont AC, Ishii H, Ballas LM, Jirousek MR, Umeda F, Nawata H, and King GL: Vitamin E prevents diabetes-induced abnormal retinal blood flow via the diacylglycerol-protein kinase C pathway. *Am J Physiology* 1995; 269:E239 -E246.
6. Aiello LP, Pierce EA, Foley ED, Takagi H, Chen H, Riddle L, Ferrara N, King GL, Smith LE: Suppression of retinal neovascularisation in vivo by inhibition of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) using soluble VEGF-receptor chimeric proteins. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 1995; 92:10457-10461.
7. Watkins PJ: Retinopathy. *BMJ* 2003; 326:924 -926.
8. Karvonen M et al. Sex differences in the incidence of insulin-dependent diabetes an analysis of the recent epidemiological data. *Diabet Metab Rev* 1997; 13:275-91.
9. Gale EAM, Gillespie KM. Diabetes and gender. *Diabetologia* 2001; 44:3-15.
10. Gale EAM. The rise of childhood type 1 diabetes in the 20th century. *Diabetes* 2002; 51:3353-61.
11. Jarosz-Chobot P et al. Rapid increase in the incidence of type 1 diabetes in Polish children from 1989 to 2004, and predictions for 2010 to 2025. *Diabetologia* 2011; 54:508-15.
12. The Relationship between Glycosylated Haemoglobin and Diabetic Retinopathy in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes - Original Article available on <http://www.turkjem.org/fulltext/the-relationship-between-glycosylated-haemoglobin-and-diabetic-retinopathy-in-patients-with-type-2-diabetes-original-article-3181>
13. The relationship between blood sugar levels (glycosylated haemoglobin) and the risk of development of diabetic retinopathy, Priyadharshini N., Annamalai R., Muthayya M.K., *International Journal of Medical Research and Review*, 2017; 5(1).